

A Suggested Reading Strategy and its Effect in Developing Reading Comprehension Skills among Higher Studies Students

Dr. Dalal Abdullah Alqiawi

Associate Professor
University of Jeddah.

Abstract- The present study aimed to suggest a strategy designed by the researcher to develop Saudi higher studies students' reading comprehension and to identify the effect of the suggested strategy on developing higher studies students' reading comprehension. The researcher followed the quasi-experimental method of a one-group pretest-posttest design. The tools used to collect data were a reading comprehension test and an interview. The results showed that the suggested strategy was effective and helped to improve participants' reading comprehension. The study participants comprised 25 higher studies students specializing in (Curriculum and Instruction and Special Education) at the Faculty of Education at the University of Jeddah. The results of the interview also supported the effectiveness of the suggested strategy because the participants confirmed that the strategy directs their reading by teaching them to activate their background knowledge and to revise the previously learned vocabulary, develop their questioning techniques, focus their attention to specific details by analyzing the text structure, visualizing the read materials to achieve better comprehension, and also supporting them in writing an informative summary of the read materials.

Key Words: Reading Comprehension, Suggested Strategy, Reding Comprehension Strategy, Language Skills, Higher Studies Students.

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a complex, interactive, adaptable, and comprehending activity that requires mastering numerous techniques and strategies. It is a cognitive skill that transforms written symbols into meaningful knowledge, ideas, and information. It helps to expand the reader's understanding by providing a lot of information in any field, depending on the reader's intent. The reader increases his/her knowledge and gets more information or ideas about a particular topic through the read material. Moreover, reading is a reciprocity skill between the reader and the writer or the reader and the text. "Reading is the ability to draw meaning from the printed page and interpret this information appropriately" (Grabe and Stoller, 2011, p.13)

The purpose of reading differs according to the interest and needs of the reader which usually increases motivation and encourages reading ability. Bojovic (2010:1) argued that "Reading purpose resides in the language learner's relationship to the learning task. The purpose is assumed to be comprehension of the message. Comprehension in instructional settings is translated into some product, such as completion of comprehension questions, a written summary, or an oral report". Kirby (2007) declared that reading comprehension is an essential foundation skill for future learning, employment, and other life skills. Reading comprehension is a fundamental skill that must be developed and refined over time to understand what is being read. Furthermore, research proves that there are different reading skills, and improving these skills can be very useful for English language learning. Reading skills are summarized as follows: skimming, scanning, intensive reading, extensive reading, and reading for comprehension. Each type of reading has its purpose and strategies. However, reading comprehension is one of the main purposes of the reading skills and can be considered the ultimate purpose of any reading activity. Reading comprehension is the primary concern of reading skills in different language courses, whether it is a native or a foreign language. The reading skill is mainly concerned with understanding the text and displaying that understanding by answering comprehension questions about some information found in the text. Reading success depends primarily on the ability to derive meaning from different printed materials and adopt the derived data for the readers' purposes.

Reading comprehension is a cognitive ability that is characterized by "the application of a skill that evolved for other purposes (listening or oral comprehension) to a new form of input (text)" (Kirby, 2007, p. 1). Thus, reading comprehension can be defined as the ability to understand a text, analyze the information, and interpret correctly what the writer wants to say. In addition, comprehension is related to the accessibility of material for recall by the reader. Mckee (2012, pp. 46-47) said that "the purpose of reading directs the understanding and the questions asked by the reader whether s/he a teacher, a student, or a normal reader. Therefore, keeping some questions in mind before

starting the reading helps the reader to look for certain information and important keywords or main ideas that will fulfill his/her concern and expand his/her knowledge".

The Problem

Many studies discussed the concept of reading comprehension and the best possible strategies that can be adopted to achieve a practical understanding of the read texts of varied subjects (Pang, 2008 & McKee, 2012). First, the learner must recognize what the author is trying to say. Then, to comprehend the read text, a person needs to be familiar with text structure and topic, aware of reading strategies, and how to use these strategies in processing material and word recognition. Karanjakwut (2017, p.1) suggests that "one of the problems of EFL students in learning the English language is the lack of reading comprehension which is an essential skill in receiving information and in the foundation of the other skills." Saudi students are not an exception; many studies indicate that although Saudi students have been studying English for a very long time, their performance in general and in reading, in particular, is not satisfactory (Al-karroud, 2005; Al-Qahtani, 2016; Al-Roomy, 2013). Yukselir (2014) recommends that teachers should be aware of their students' reading strategies. He adds, "They should introduce their students to useful reading strategies which would increase their comprehension when reading English academic materials." According to the results, it is crucial to encourage, develop, and strengthen students' reading comprehension skills by presenting them with a variety of reading strategies. "Both rely on prior knowledge or system knowledge, and the application of cognitive and affective strategies are means of acquiring or changing understanding." (DaCosta & Gutierrez, 2020, p.4).

Higher studies students resort to reading, in English in specific, for many purposes in a wide range of texts, including books, journal articles, internet articles, newspapers, research reports and literature reviews. They mainly read to collect information and review research to write their own. During the reading process, they must understand texts, criticize, evaluate, compare and contrast them, and derive usefulness. In a pilot study carried out by the researcher at the University of Jeddah with students of various specializations (Special Needs and Curriculum and Instruction), it was discovered that students read many texts related to their field of specialization and that their concern is mainly with understanding the main idea, the supporting arguments, the concept, and the conclusion of the read texts. However, 95% of the respondents agreed that reading comprehension and the best strategy to be followed to achieve the purpose of reading is the main difficulty they usually encounter.

Besides, the practical experience of the researcher as a supervisor of master students approved that students have troubles in selecting the appropriate strategy they can adopt to be successful and effective readers who can read, analyze, synthesize, or evaluate what they are reading. These skills are best taught through direct teaching as suggested by (Kirby, 2007, p. 1, Grabe, 1991, p. 377, Krashen, 2013, Grabe & Stoller, 2014, p.20-2). Therefore, the present research intends to present a suggested strategy to help higher studies students read, understand, and tackle the best texts among the massive amount of available information that best fulfills their research purpose.

Questions

1. What is the suggested strategy that can be adopted by higher studies students to develop their reading comprehension of texts?
2. What is the effect of the suggested strategy on developing the reading comprehension of higher studies students?
3. How to reinforce the results obtained from the test about the effect of the suggested strategy on the development of the reading comprehension of higher studies students?

Objectives

1. Suggesting a strategy designed by the researcher to develop higher studies students' reading comprehension.
2. Identifying the effect of the suggested strategy on the development of higher studies students' reading comprehension.
3. Developing an interview to reinforce the results obtained from the posttest concerning the effect of the suggested strategy in developing reading comprehension of higher studies students.

Significance

1. Providing the literature on reading comprehension with a concentrated analysis of some effective strategies in developing reading comprehension of texts.
2. Fulfilling one of Education's vital current purposes: developing students' literacy, especially reading comprehension.
3. Helping higher studies students develop their reading and comprehension skills to be effective and successful readers.

Delimitation

1. The strategy will be delimited to the reading comprehension skills that are usually used to understand the overall meaning of a text, deduce the main idea and supporting details, connect the text details with students' previous knowledge, and find out the conclusion.
2. The subjects are delimited to higher studies students at the University of Jeddah (Special Education and Curriculum and Instruction master students) in 2022.

Definition of Terms

Reading Comprehension: Reading comprehension is "the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language" (Snow, 2010, p. 11).

Reading Comprehension Strategy: Reading comprehension strategy is a cognitive or behavioral action enacted under particular contextual conditions, aiming to improve some aspect of comprehension. Proficient readers use cognitive and metacognitive reading strategies such as setting goals before they begin to read, asking themselves questions and answering them while reading, summarizing, and reflecting on what they read.

Literature Review

- Reading Comprehension

Reading comprehension is one of the most complicated skills one needs to acquire. Reading comprehension refers to the capacity to read, analyze, and comprehend text. It depends on two interconnected skills: language comprehension and word reading (Zimmerman and Hutchins, 2003). Reading comprehension varies in purpose: sometimes the teacher asks questions to check students' understanding, and other times it is requested by the reader/ students to review or evaluate his/her knowledge. In addition, it helps in mastering the foreign language when understanding the meaning of new words and getting acquainted with their structure and spelling.

Reading comprehension is a cognitive and interactive activity that depends on the interaction between the reader and the text to get the correct meaning. It is mainly a process of understanding what the content means, getting the purpose, the main and sub ideas, and some other details depending on the purpose of reading. Reading comprehension aims to translate the read symbols into significant ideas and benefit from this understanding in using the information and adopting the knowledge in new situations.

Carrell and Eisterhold (1983) conclude that EFL/ESL reading theory has been influenced during the past decades by Goodman (from the mid-to-late 1970s), who views reading as a "guessing game" in which the "reader reconstructs, as best as s/he can, a message which a writer has encoded. Moreover, Reading comprehension is defined as the capacity to quickly and effectively recognize words, acquire and use an extensive vocabulary, process sentences to increase comprehension and engage in a variety of strategic processes and underlying cognitive skills, such as goal-setting, flexible goal-changing, and comprehension monitoring. These procedures also involve interpreting text meaning in light of prior knowledge and solving and assessing texts in light of the objectives and goals of readers (Grabe, 2014, Vongkrachang & Chinwonno, 2015, Alyousef, 2006).

However, Collins and Smith (1980) believe that teaching comprehension monitoring and hypothesis elaboration and evaluation are two crucial components of the comprehension process. The ability of the students to assess their ongoing comprehension processes while reading a text and take corrective action is known as comprehension monitoring. Students must also be able to use textual cues to form hypotheses about what is occurring or is likely to occur, evaluate these hypotheses as new information is gathered, and revise them if they are incorrect.

Reading comprehension is a constructivist theory-based process as the reader uses all the background knowledge, ideas, information, and attitudes to understand the text. Much research states that reading comprehension requires updating the mental representation of the text's meaning, known as mental models or situation models (Johnson-Laird, 1983; Kintsch, 1998). The reader interacts with the text using his/her background knowledge to build his/her conceptions, ideas, meanings, and sometimes judgment about the text or the writer of that text. Reading comprehension is not a matter of decoding or skimming through texts to understand what is written, but a process of using the student's background, purpose, and skills to develop a product from that text. "Readers make use of their existing background knowledge (schemata) to make predictions about what is coming next in the text and about how some new, unfamiliar piece of information relates to what is already known" (Bojovic, 2010, p.)

Comprehension depends on two processing abilities, both of which must be taught. First, the reader must monitor his or her ongoing processing for potential comprehension failures and take corrective action when failures are discovered. Second, utilizing textual cues to create, assess, and revise hypotheses about the text's present and future events (Collins & Smith, 1980).

Grabe and Stoller (2011) outlined how reading comprehension processes were likely to work for fluent readers by dividing the explanation into two parts: lower- and higher-level functions. The lower-level operations represented the more automatic linguistic processes and were viewed as more skill-oriented. The higher-level processes generally represented comprehension, involving interpreting the texts, combining reading strategies, making inferences, and

drawing extensively on background knowledge. As a result of understanding the text, the reader comes up with a summary, main and sub-ideas, answers some questions, fills in gaps, and some times presents a report.

Moore, McClelland, Alef, and Vogel (2016) added that when students are actively reading, processing what they read, visualizing it, summarizing, and making inferences, they try to understand and relate to the text's meaning. Gough and Tunmer (1986) and Tunmer and Chapman (2012) argued that there are two components of reading: the decoding skill, which is the ability to pronounce words fluently while reading printed text, and language comprehension, where vocabulary knowledge plays a very vital role in understanding the text. By doing this, students exercise critical thinking to balance the author's intent and their understanding of the text.

Reading Comprehension Strategies

Reading comprehension strategy is a cognitive or behavioural action enacted under particular contextual conditions to improve some aspect of comprehension. Acquisition of better reading strategies is needed to remove the illusion of understanding among readers suffering from low comprehension standards. They need to acquire and implement strategies to facilitate a more profound understanding. Students need to adopt specific strategies and techniques to achieve the goals they aim at from their reading. Bojovic (2010) divides these strategies into three main stages; under each stage, there are many sub-skills or techniques. The three stages comprise the following: the pre-reading stage, which includes predicting, word association, discussions, and text surveys. Then the while reading stage contains a list of questions, scanning and skimming activities, working out the meaning of unfamiliar words, pattern study guides, summarising, clarifying, questioning, predicting, etc. Finally, the post-reading stage includes reviewing the content, working on grammar, vocabulary in context or word roots, and discourse features, and relating the new information to the student's previous knowledge, interests, opinions, discussions, debates, role-plays, and project work. "The outcome of reading comprehension is the mental representation of a text meaning that is combined with the readers' previous knowledge." (Gilakajani and Sabouri, 2016, p. 230).

Many researchers have written about the importance of reading strategies in developing reading comprehension, mainly if the readers include a certain subject or a specific topic. They cultivate their memories and use their background knowledge to help them understand the reading text. Anderson and Pearson (1984) emphasized the importance of activating the reader's memory and using background knowledge to understand the text. Gilakajani and Sabouri (2016) added that cognitive scientists stated that successful reading strategies are used to relate readers' previous knowledge to new information they face in the texts. If the reader is concentrating and looking for certain information or specific topics, Wood, Woloshyn, and Willoughby (1995) concluded that generating and asking questions during the reading process is vital in understanding that text.

Paris, Lipson, and Wixson (1983) argued that the metacognitive turn helped to understand that reading involves many kinds of knowledge. First is declarative knowledge, which entails familiarity with both the general world and the world of text (prototypical structures and authorial devices). Second is procedural knowledge, which covers all methods for monitoring, assessing, and repairing comprehension. The third type is conditional knowledge, which entails understanding when and why a specific strategy (in preference to others) would be used to improve the reader's comprehension. Semtin and Maniam (2015, p.3) associated Cognitive Reading Strategies with "specific learning tasks employed in the learning process, such as relating the new words in mind and writing down the main idea." These strategies assist and guide the students to understand the reading content through rereading the text, scanning, analyzing, and summarizing. They also include using the first language to produce ideas. Semtin and Maniam (2015, p.55) described the Metacognitive Strategy as a technique that requires "planning for learning, thinking about the learning process, monitoring of one's comprehension, and evaluating learning after completing a task." Ali and Razali (2019, p. 4) discussed the concept of Metacognitive Reading Strategies and explained that they are concerned with mainly three strategies, namely, 1) Problem-Solving, 2) Global Reading, and 3) Support Reading.

Other researchers like Anderson and Pearson (1984) and Hansen and Pearson (1983) emphasized that "Being able to make inferences is an important factor for readers' successful reading." Another important factor that helps to activate readers' understanding and make what is read clearer is predicting the meaning from the title "The title of a text can operate memories of texts with the same content, permitting them to guess the content of a new text." (Gillet and Temple, 1994, p.235). Summarizing is also an influential factor in helping the reader understand the essential ideas in a text. Gilakajani and Sabouri (2016, p.235) added that through summarization, "... readers can be aware of text structure, of what is significant in a text, and of how opinions are related to each other". Gilakajani and Sabouri also emphasized the significance of visualizing, which is taking a mental picture of the text to comprehend processes the reader encounters during reading (2010, p.235). Gilakajani and Sabouri notice (2010) agreed with Pressley's (1976), who stated that "Readers who form a mental image as they read are better able to remember what they have read than those who do not image."(p. 356). Paris, Wasik and Turner (1991) explained that successful readers use "fix-up" strategies to improve their understanding. These strategies include rereading, reading ahead, explaining the words by looking them up in a dictionary or asking someone for assistance.

Successful readers generally resort to strategies to clarify meaning and comprehend what they read. These strategies can be taught and learned, as Gilakajani and Sabouri (2016, p.236) inferred that "A lot of students can gain from explicit instruction that teaches them to apply particular strategies for understanding a text." Honig, Diamond and Gutlohn (2000) declared that "particular comprehension strategies can be taught and learned and that their conscious use can help readers to ameliorate their comprehension." Effective teachers can use strategies that prove successful in raising students' ability to read and understand texts, deduce information and write a valuable summary or report.

Higher Studies students are good examples of readers that rely significantly on the reading comprehension strategies to get the information they need. They read books, scientific articles, and research to increase understanding or document their studies. However, this reading process should be purposeful and directed toward specific information, and this goal cannot be achieved without understanding the content. "Reading for a purpose provides motivation - an important aspect of being a good reader" (Bojovic, 2010). When reading and analyzing a text, higher studies students, like many other readers, need to know the main idea, the sub-ideas, the objectives, the tools, the methodology, the statistical method, and the concluding results of any research. Therefore, reading comprehension is critical to get what they want from the read text.

In higher studies, students usually read a type of informational text. They read abstracts, scientific articles, research, or books and they usually look for specific information while reading. They read mainly in their field of specialization, using their previous knowledge, concepts, and terms to understand the text. They usually read to get specific information and to produce an abstract of what they read. They must read with comprehension and adopt specific effective strategies to achieve their desired goals.

Methodology

Method: A pre-and post-test one group-experimental design was adopted to identify the effect of the suggested strategy in developing reading comprehension among higher studies students. The independent variable was the suggested strategy, and the dependent variable was reading comprehension among higher studies students.

Participants: The research population comprised all the higher studies students in both Special Education and Curriculum and Instruction departments, representing the study subjects. The two groups are 15 from the Special Education Department and 10 from the Curriculum and Instruction Department. Both are studying at the College of Education to achieve a master's degree in their specialization.

Instrumentation

1. The research material consisted of the suggested strategy for developing the reading comprehension of higher studies students. The strategy consisted of; goals, methods of teaching the strategy, content and activities, teaching aids, and evaluation.
2. The pre and posttest consisted of 20 questions that were applied before and after teaching the strategy to assess the effect of the strategy in developing the participants' reading comprehension. (See Appendix A)
3. The interview was applied to the subjects to make sure of the posttest results and the suggested strategy's positive effect on the subjects' reading comprehension. (See Appendix B)

First: The test

The following process estimated the Validity and Reliability of the test:

Validity was assessed by two methods:

- a. Face Validity: was estimated by submitting the test to a group of reviewers who are specialized in Education, Teaching English as a Foreign language, and Methods of research. The total number was 5, and they were asked to express their views on the validity of the questions to assess the accuracy of their formulation, linguistic integrity, and the clarity of their meanings. The researcher accepted the reviewers' suggestions for developing the test. The test questions concentrated on the main parts that should be covered when reading related studies and doing a literature review of a study.
- b. Internal Validity: the internal consistency of the test was estimated by applying it to an exploratory sample of about (25) students other than the research sample and collecting data using "Pearson Correlations" to assess the internal consistency of the test.

Table (1) Shows Pearson Correlation and Its significance for the Test Items

Item	Correlation factor						
1	**0.744	6	**0.672	11	**0.658	16	**0.672
2	**0.692	7	**0.677	12	**0.667	17	**0.661
3	*0.562	8	*0.510	13	*0.528	18	*0.513
4	**0.687	9	*0.505	14	**0.751	19	*0.510

5	**0.657	10	**0.664	15	**0.699	20	**0.766
** Significant at 0.01		* Significant at 0.05					

Table (1) shows that the correlation coefficients between the test items and the total score were suitable for scientific research. They were all significant at a significance level less than (0.05).

Reliability

Reliability of the test was estimated using two methods, as follows:

a. Half-segmentation Method: the Reliability of the test was assessed by splitting it into odd and double numbers of questions; after applying it to an exploratory sample other than the study sample and via using the Guttman coefficient for mid-segmentation, the reliability of the test according to the split half was significant as shown in table (2).

Table (2): Test Reliability coefficients using the split-half Method.

The Test	Guttman Factor	Significance
Two halves of the test (odds and doubles)	0.85	0.01

Table (2) shows that the reliability of the split-half Method amounted to (.85), which is significant at the level of (0.01), and which is an acceptable degree for scientific research.

b. The Spearman Method: the reliability of the test was measured using the Spearman method, where the reliability coefficient was assessed between each question and the test's total score. Table (3) shows these results:

Table (3) Test Reliability coefficients by Spearman Method

Question	correlation coefficient	Question	correlation coefficient
1	*0.544	11	*0.534
2	*0.532	12	**0.616
3	**0.611	13	**0.601
4	**0.692	14	**0.636
5	**0.683	15	**0.615
6	*0.512	16	**0.619
7	*0.510	17	*0.518
8	**0.619	18	**0.611
9	**0.607	19	**0.667
10	**0.612	20	**0.654
** Significant at 0.01		* Significant at 0.05	

Table (3) shows that the reliability of the test according to the Spearman method is acceptable for scientific research, as they were all significant at a level less than (0.05).

Determining the coefficient of difficulty and ease of the test questions:

The question difficulty coefficient was calculated in the test used in this study by using the following equation:

First: the Difficulty coefficient (the number of students who answered wrongly / the total number of students)

Second: the Ease coefficient (the number of students who answered correctly / the total number of students) and table

(4) shows the coefficient of difficulty and ease of the test questions.

Table (4) Determination of the coefficient of difficulty and ease of test questions

Question	wrong answers	Total No. of students	Difficulty Factor	Ease Factor	Question	wrong answers	Total No. of students	Difficulty Factor	Ease Factor
1	8	25	% 32	% 68	11	11	25	%44	% 54
2	9	25	% 36	%0	12	10	25	% 40	% 60
3	13	25	% 52	% 48	13	9	25	% 36	% 64
4	13	25	% 52	% 48	14	10	25	% 40	% 60
5	10	25	% 40	% 60	15	9	25	% 36	% 64
6	10	25	% 40	% 60	16	11	25	%44	% 54
7	10	25	% 40	% 60	17	10	25	% 40	% 60
8	10	25	% 40	% 60	18	10	25	% 40	% 60

9	10	25	% 40	% 60	19	10	25	% 40	% 60
10	9	25	% 36	% 64	20	9	25	% 36	% 64

Table (4) indicates that all degrees of difficulty for the test were between 32-52. This result shows an appropriate difficulty of the test questions, which are acceptable for scientific research.

Calculating the discrimination coefficient for the test:

The discrimination coefficient for the test questions has been determined by the following:

1. Applying the test to the study sample consisted of (25) female students.
2. The students' papers are arranged in ascending order according to grades.
3. The papers are divided into two groups, upper and lower, representing the highest 25% of the papers with the highest grades and the lowest 25% with the lowest degrees.
4. Thus, the number of participants of the upper group is (6) female students, and the number of participants of the lower group is (6).
5. The discrimination coefficient was calculated for each test question in table (5) according to the following formula:

The number of students who answered the question in the upper group - The number of students who responded to the question in the lower group.

Discrimination factor = $\frac{\text{Upper} - \text{Lower}}{\text{Upper} + \text{Lower}} \times 100$

Half of the total number x value of the question (1)

Table (5) Determination of the discrimination coefficient for test questions

Question	Upper Students	Lower Students	Discrimination Factor	Question	Upper Students	Lower Students	Discrimination Factor
1	6	2	%66.6	11	5	1	%66.6
2	5	2	%50	12	6	1	%83.3
3	6	1	%83.3	13	6	3	%50
4	5	1	%66.6	14	5	1	%66.6
5	6	2	%66.6	15	5	1	%66.6
6	6	1	%83.3	16	6	2	%66.6
7	5	2	%50	17	5	1	%66.6
8	4	1	%50	18	6	1	%83.3
9	5	1	%66.6	19	6	3	%50
10	6	2	%66.6	20	5	1	%66.6

Table (5) indicates that all the test questions were distinct, with the lowest discrimination coefficient (50%) and the highest discrimination coefficient (83.3%).

Second: The Interview

To support the test results in the second question and evaluate how accurately the test results represent the participant's understanding of the strategy, the researcher constructed a semi-structured interview of 10 questions. The gist of discussion was concentrating on the strategy, its practicality, clearness, and easiness. The interview consisted of 10 open-ended questions about the steps followed by participants while reading a study selected by the researcher and related to the participant's specialization. The data collected from the interviews were read multiple times to identify common answers about the strategy and assess the level of agreement between participants.

The following process estimated the Validity and Reliability of the interview:

- Validity

To assess the validity of the interview, the researcher adopted the following steps:

- a. The purpose: The purpose of the interview was aligned with the test purpose and focused on measuring the participants understanding of the strategy and their ability to apply each step accordingly.
- b. Peer Review: The interview was given to a group of reviewers specialized in education and methods of research to provide their feedback on the questions and if they assessed the same data obtained from the test. The reviewers' responses were considered for refining the interview questions and design the interview in its final form.

- Reliability

- a. Compre information: The researcher compared the information obtained during the interview with data collected from the test. The results were identical and the interviewee agreed that the questions really checked their understanding of the strategy.

b. Evaluate the structure and format: The researcher made sure the questions of the interview are clear, focused, and relevant to the main concept of the research which is the suggested strategy. The interviewee responses and willingness to provide information were also considered in ensuring the interview reliability.

Findings and Discussion

To answer the research questions and achieve its objectives, the researcher adopted the following steps:

Q.1. To answer the first question (What is the suggested strategy that can be adopted by higher studies students to develop their reading comprehension of texts?)

The researcher systematically analyzed the related studies that discussed reading comprehension strategies and the procedures that should be adopted to develop reading comprehension. These studies were discussed in detail in the literature review of the present research. The analysis resulted in several identical procedures in some steps and different in others. Therefore, the researcher designed the strategy by tackling the most frequently recommended steps and the ones that are appropriate for the level and needs of higher studies students. The analysis resulted in the following strategy.

The suggested strategy:

1. Activating background knowledge

- A. Bridge your old knowledge with the new information in the passage.
- B. Ask simple questions like: "what do I know about (a particular topic)" and "what is/are the objective/s, method, results etc.?" "The objective of such questions is to stimulate your previous knowledge of the topic.
- C. Connect the reading passage to your already existing knowledge by looking for familiar words that are required in your search like title, objective, aim, tool, sample, results etc.,
- D. Start working your way up from the already existing schema.
- E. Write a short outline of what you have read including the following details: title, main idea, sub ideas, importance, etc.,

2. Questioning

- A. Prepare certain questions like:
 1. what is the title of the read passage?
 2. what is the writer intent?
 3. what is the method s/he is using?
 4. are there any specific details that of more importance to me?
 5. what is the relation between what I am reading and my concern?
- B. Reflect on three main questions:
 1. A right now question: A 'right now question' focuses on the material presented. What is the essence of the material read? What are the facts that are being mentioned?
 2. An analytical question: An 'analytical question' requires you to reflect on what you have learnt. What does the author want me to understand from this material?
 3. A research question: A 'research question' encourages you to look for information beyond what is in the text. This allows for more comprehensive active learning to occur.

3. Analysing text structure

- A. Analyse or comprehend the structure of a text. (The tenses that should be used in writing related studies and the items to be covered, the number of words)
- B. Identify the pattern by which writers organize their material. (Procedures- statistics)
- C. Understanding the pattern in which the material is presented; is it cause-effect pattern, problem-solution pattern, or a descriptive pattern like a list, web or a matrix pattern allows the students to comprehend the information better.
- D. Teach all the patterns of a text structure to the students, as each structure is different and takes time to learn.
- E. Make use of sub-headings, labels, captions, tables, graphs, etc. as these help students to understand the material better.

4. Visualizing

- A. Visualize the material because forming visual images in your head as you read the text will help in better comprehension. (How the procedures of the research went on and how can you benefit from it, compare the present research with your own, what you can follow and what will you change or add?)
- B. Look for main results and statistics that are related to your own interest and draw a picture about your own written report, how will you discuss/ present your own?
- C. Give special critical reflection to demonstration and discussion of results as your own will be usually very similar.

D. Visualize them as structural images or diagrams instead of mere pictures, as pictures tend to fade.

5. Summarizing

- Summarize the material read; the ability to summarize enhances comprehension.
- Delete irrelevant details, combine similar ideas, condense main ideas, and connect major themes into concise statements that capture the purpose of the reading for you.
- Make use of the other four strategies will find it easier to summarize the material.
- Summarize the material in the form of diagrams, mind maps, tables, or lists either visually or in writing.

Q.2. To answer the second question: (What is the effect of the suggested strategy on developing the reading comprehension of higher studies students?). The researcher adopted the following steps:

a. The reading comprehension pretest was applied on participants to assess their level of comprehension before applying the strategy. The next step was to re-apply the strategy on participants and to explain the steps of the strategy one by one and to ask for application of each step on a text related to their specialization; the same text is used for each step of the strategy. The explanation for each step lasted for one session of fifty minutes. The total number of sessions was five for the whole strategy.

After completing the strategy, a reading comprehension posttest was adopted on participants to check the effect of the strategy on their reading comprehension. To determine the effect of the proposed strategy on the development of reading comprehension among postgraduate students, the students' scores were calculated on the pre- and post-measurement test, by using the T-test, and Table No. (6) shows these results.

Table (6): The results of the (t) test for the comparison between the means of postgraduate students on the pre and post measurement

Test	No.	SMA	St. D	(T) Value	Sig.	Eta square	Effect Size
pretest	25	9.920	2.234	2.517	0.001	0.684	high
posttest	25	16.580	6.368				

The results presented in Table (6) indicated that there were statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha \leq 0.001$) between the pre and posttest of postgraduate students, in favor of the posttest, whose mean was (16.580), while the mean on the pretest was (9.920), and this indicates that there was a high effect of the proposed strategy on the development of reading comprehension among postgraduate students. Furthermore, the ETA square shows that the size of the effect is large because it is more than (0.50). This is based on the criterion set by Creswell (2018) as shown in Table 7.

Table (7) Levels of effect size for each test of effect size

Statistical tool	Effect Size		
Eta Square	Small	Medium	Large
	Less than 0.29	30- Less than 50	50.0 and more

Q.3 To answer the third question: (How to reinforce the results obtained from the test about the effect of the suggested strategy on the development of the reading comprehension of higher studies students?), The researcher adopted a semi structured interview to check the participants opinion about the strategy and to reinforce the results of the posttest. The answers of the interview supported the posttest results and the participants confirmed that the strategy was effective and that it helped them to focus their reading of the related studies on certain points which improved their comprehension and speed their reading process. They asserted that the strategy directed their reading to look first for the title and the abstract of the study which motivates them to activate their background knowledge and the previously acquired vocabulary. Then, they started to look for the study objectives, tools, statistical methods, and conclusion which supported their understanding and accelerated their reading. They also stated that the strategy was clear and easy to adopt and concluded that it encouraged them to read more in foreign studies and not to depend only on Arabic studies.

In summary the suggested strategy aimed to increase higher studies students' participation and reinforce their reading comprehension and motivation, enhance their abilities to understand the read material and direct their attention to specific details, and support them to prepare for an essay or report submission or even for a test. It consisted of five practical and easy to adopt steps. These steps are as follows: Activating background knowledge, Questioning, Analysing text structure, Visualizing, and Summarizing.

The strategy was clear, applicable, reliable and valid enough to be adopted by higher studies students. Its effectiveness appeared in the significant difference between means of participants performance in the pre and posttest that the t-test

value reached to 2.517 and the Eta square reached to 0.684 and that was a high level of effectiveness. The participants responses about the strategy during the interview also supported this result regarding the participant's positive opinions about the strategy, their direct application of the strategy and their willingness to adopt it in their reading process hereafter.

Recommendation and Suggestions

The study recommended that reading comprehension strategies should be directly taught in the classroom and that more attention should be given to reading comprehension and the best appropriate method to achieve it. Reading comprehension should be organized and directly taught to students from the beginning as it is one of the vital skills required among current skills and in international tests as well. The study also recommended creating appropriate educational environment for students and paying concentrated attention to students' needs in the field of reading in general and reading comprehension in particular.

The following are suggestions for further research:

1. Investigating the effectiveness of the strategy in developing reading comprehension skills of students in other stages and other learning areas.
2. Investigating the effectiveness of the strategy in developing reading comprehension skills for students with learning disabilities.
3. Investigating the effectiveness of a program designed to train teachers on how to implement the strategy on reading classes.
4. Examining teachers' perception of using the strategy in teaching the English language reading skill.

REFERENCES:

1. Al-Karroud, I. (2005). New, interesting methods and techniques: English as it should be taught. *Al-Ma'rifah Journal*
2. Al-Qahtani, A. (2016). Why do Saudi EFL readers exhibit poor reading abilities? *English Language and Literature Studies*, 6(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ells.v6n1p1>
3. Al-Roomy, M. (2013). An action research study of collaborative strategic reading in English with Saudi medical students (PhD thesis). University of Sussex, UK
4. Ali, A. & Rzali, A (2019). A Review of Studies on Cognitive and Metacognitive Reading Strategies in Teaching Reading Comprehension for ESL/EFL Learners. *English Language Teaching*; Vol. 12, No. 6
5. Alyousef, H. (2006). Teaching Reading Comprehension to ESL/EFL Learners. *Journal of Language and Learning*. Vol, 5. No. 1. ISSN 1475 - 8989
6. Anderson, R. C., & Pearson, P. D. (1984). A schema-theoretic view of basic processes in reading. In P. D. Pearson, R. Barr, M. L. Kamil, & P. Mosenthal (Eds.), *Handbook of reading research* (pp. 255–292). New York: Longman. Retrieved from <http://hdl.handle.net/2142/31284>
7. Bojovic, M. (2010) *Reading Skills and Reading Comprehension in English for Specific Purposes*. Research Gate. Celje, Slovenia
8. Carrell, P. & Eisterhold, J. (1983). Schema theory and ESL reading pedagogy. *TESOL Quarterly*, 17(4).
9. Collins, A & Smith, E. (1980). *Teaching the Process Of Reading Comprehension*. Technical Report No. 182. Center for the Study of Reading. University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign
10. Dacosta, p. & Gutierrez, Y. (2020). Level of Reading Comprehension of Dominican EFL College Students. Santo Domingo, D.R.
11. Gilakajani, A & Sabouri, N. (2016). How Can Students Improve Their Reading Comprehension Skill?. *Journal of Studies in Education*. Vol.6, No.2. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5296/jse.v6i2.9201>
12. Gillet, J. W., & Temple, C. (1994). *Understanding reading problems: Assessment and instruction* (4th ed.). New York: Harper Collins.
13. Gough, P. B., & Tunmer, W. E. (1986). Decoding, reading and reading disability. *Remedial and Special Education*, 7, 6–10. doi:10.1177/074193258600700104
14. Grabe, W. & Stoller, F. (2011). *Teaching and researching reading*. NY: Pearson Education Limited.
15. Grabe, W. & Stoller, F. L. (2014). *Teaching reading for academic purposes*. In M. Celce-Murcia
16. Grabe, W. (1991). Current Developments in Second Language Reading Research, *TESOL Quarterly*, Vol. 25, Issue, 3
17. Grabe, W. (2014). Key issues in L2 reading development. In X. Deng, & R. Seow (Eds.), *Alternative Pedagogies in the English Language and Communication Classroom* Singapore: NUS.
18. Hansen, J., & Pearson, P. D. (1983). An instructional study: Improving the inferential comprehension of fourth grade good and poor readers. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 75(6), 821–829. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.75.6.821>

19. Hansen, J., & Pearson, P. D. (1983). An instructional study: Improving the inferential comprehension of fourth grade good and poor readers. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 75(6), 821–829. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.75.6.821>
20. Honig, W., Diamond, L., & Gutlohn, L. (Eds.). (2000). *Teaching reading sourcebook for kindergarten through eighth grade*. Novato, CA: Arena Press; National Reading Panel.
21. Johnson-Laird, P. N. (1983). *Mental Models. Towards a Cognitive Science of Language, Inference and Consciousness*. Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
22. Karanjakwut, C. (2017). The P3C2R+GIRD Paradigm of Creating a Reading Comprehension Lesson for EFL Students: From Conceptual Model to Model Lesson. *Journal of Education and Practice* www.iiste.org ISSN 2222-1735 (Paper) ISSN 2222-288X (Online) Vol.8, No.32
23. Kintsch, W. (1998). *Comprehension: A paradigm for cognition*. New York: Cambridge University Press.
24. Kirby, John. (2007) *Reading Comprehension: Its Nature and Development*. Canadian Literacy Research Network. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/242598620> . pp. 1-8
25. Krashen, S. (2013). Should we teach strategies? *Electronic Journal of Foreign Language Teaching*, 10(1): 35-39. Retrieved from <http://e-flt.nus.edu.sg/v10n12013/krashen.pdf>
26. Mckee, S. (2012). *Reading Comprehension, What We Know: A Review of Research 1995 to 2011* Language Testing in Asia, Volume two, Issue one February
27. Moore, J. McClelland, S. Alef, E. and Vogel, E. (2016). The Simplicity and Complexity of Reading Comprehension. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*. Vol.7, No.6
28. Pang, J. (2008). Research on good and poor reader characteristics: Implications for L2 reading research in China. *Reading in a Foreign Language*, 20(1)
29. Paris, S. C., Wasik, B. A., & Turner, J. C. (1991). The development of strategic readers. In R. Barr, M. L. Kamil, P. B. Mosenthal, & P. D. Pearson (Eds.), *Handbook of reading research* (Vol. 2, pp. 609–640). New York: Longman.
30. Paris, S., Lipson, M., & Wixson, K. (1983). Becoming a Strategic Reader. *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 8, 293-316. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-476X\(83\)90018-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-476X(83)90018-8)
31. Pressley, G. M. (1976). Mental imagery helps eight-year-olds remember what they read. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 68(3), 355–359. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.68.3.355>
32. Semtin, S., & Maniam, M. (2015). Reading strategies among ESL Malaysian secondary school students. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, 4(2)
33. Snow (2010). *Reading Comprehension: Reading for Learning*, Harvard Graduate School of Education, Cambridge, MA, USA 2010 Elsevier Ltd.
34. Tunmer, W. & Chapman, J. (2012). The simple view of reading redux: Vocabulary knowledge and the independent components hypothesis. *Journal of Learning Disabilities*, 45, 453–466. doi:10.1177/00222194111432685
35. Vongkrachang, S. & Chinwonno, A. (2015). CORI: Explicit Reading Instruction to Enhance Informational Text Comprehension and Reading Engagement for Thai EFL Students. *PASAA* Volume 49
36. Wood, E., Woloshyn, V. E., & Willoughby, T. (1995). *Cognitive strategy instruction for middle and high schools*. Cambridge, MA: Brookline Books.
37. Yukselir, C. (2014). An investigation into the reading strategy use of EFL prep-class students. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 158, 65-72. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.12.034>
38. Zimmerman, S. and Hutchins, C. (2003) *Seven keys to comprehension: How to help your kids read it and get it!* New York: Three Rivers Press.